

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_1_2	
Title	System for Community Liaison.
Category	Socio-cultural
Purpose of the method	System for Community Liaison (SYCL) is a proprietary software developed by Anatrack Ltd, used by administrators to create and manage networks of inter-linked websites, on which content creation is simplified for volunteers with minimal training
Effort in time	Can be used within an hour of tutorial use and competently with a 1-day course. Ease of use is 3-4/5.
Number of objects investigated	No limits – currently 114 instances are operative.
Data format	HTML, also proprietary code, in SQL databases.
Description	A back-office for administrators handles users, translation (currently 15 languages), websites and pages which can occur in one language across many sites. Individual sites can support registration, forums, image galleries, maps with routes, and a variety of page and site formats. Content is written by site editors, who may also have publisher rights, on WYSIWYG editors that convert to HTML. The system is constrained to non-commercial use by a licence with not-for-profit third parties who manage the networks
Basic Literature	There is a tutorial site at: https://sycl-uk.sycl.net/1/getting-started-with-sycl

Contact person within the project	Robert Kenward, reke@ceh.ac.uk , Pro-Coast Coordination Nick Casey, nick@anatrack.com , software engineer
Linked material	<i>The system links to Morphmaster to create networks at, e.g.,</i> https://www.pro-coast.eu https://www.naturalliance.org <i>but also runs many stand-alone websites, e.g.,</i> https://esug.sycl.net https://arne-parish-council.sycl.net/1/arne-parish